

The Device for the Direct Measurement of Sample Temperature Reactivity with 300 °C of Sample Temperature in Research Reactor, UTR-KINKI

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ABSTRACT

The MoveluX™ microreactor core uses calcium-hydride as the moderator material due to its high hydrogen dissociation temperature, hydrogen density, small neutron capture cross-section, and cost. This core exhibits a positive temperature-reactivity coefficient in the low-temperature region, which results from the neutron-spectrum shift associated with temperature changes. The core neutronics design utilizes the positive temperature reactivity characteristics to ensure critical safety during reactor transportation. The core neutronics characteristics based on the neutron thermal equilibrium condition change depend on the moderator temperature, and this spectrum shift was confirmed experimentally. Consequently, the thermal scattering law (TSL) data of the calcium-hydride dominates the core neutronics characteristics. However, the TSL data of the calcium-hydride was only measured in 2004. Additionally, integral experiment data at higher temperatures are not available. A sample-temperature-increasing device, named Strauss, was developed for direct measurement of sample reactivity within the UTR-KINKI reactor core. This device is installed in the center of the UTR-KINKI core, and can increase the sample temperature by up to 300 °C. The regulation requires device surface temperature below 60 °C during the experiment; as a result, the Strauss device kept less than 50 °C. Moreover, the reactivity worth of the Strauss device was measured based on the positive and negative reactor period, and it was around -300 pcm. Furthermore, the temperature reactivity of the calcium-hydride was evaluated 10 pcm between room temperature and 300 °C by simulation. As the next step, temperature reactivity of the calcium-hydride will be measured at the UTR-KINKI.

Keywords: Reactor experiment, calcium-hydride, temperature reactivity, TSL, $S(\alpha, \beta)$

1. INTRODUCTION

The Toshiba Energy Systems & Solutions Corporation has been developing the MoveluX™ microreactor since 2017. In the core design, calcium-hydride (CaH_2) was selected from the viewpoint of the hydrogen density and the small neutron capture cross-section of calcium, as well as the cost. Additionally, the CaH_2 neutron moderator material can be used under high-temperature conditions up to 800 °C.[1]

The core exhibits positive temperature reactivity at low temperatures, transitioning to negative values near the operating temperature of approximately 800 °C. The neutronics design of the core utilizes its characteristics for criticality safety during reactor transportation [2-3]. As a result, the MoveluX™ core

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realizes a core that cannot be achieved under critical conditions without both the safety rod extraction and the forced heating, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

These core neutronics characteristics are based on the neutron spectrum shift into the moderator due to the change in the thermal equilibrium conditions, and it was confirmed experimentally by J. Lee [4]. This neutron spectrum shift is exhibited by the upscattering reaction interaction with hydrogen. Consequently, the thermal scattering law (TSL) data of the CaH_2 dominate the core neutronics characteristics.

However, the TSL of the CaH_2 was only measured in 2004 by P. Morris [5], and measured at room temperature. This evaluation is used for the TSL data stored in JEFF-3.3. On the other hand, ENDF-B/VIII.1 stored TSL of CaH_2 based on the first-principles calculation [6]. Therefore, high-temperature experiment-based TSL data of the CaH_2 are not available in the published nuclear data libraries.

Figure 1. The reactivity characteristics of the MoveluX™ core.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the criticality safety during the transportation.

Moreover, only a few integral experiments, namely, reactivity worth experiments for the CaH_2 samples, were performed by T. Sano; however, the temperature condition was room temperature [7]. As the experiment method, reactivity worth measurement using the research reactor can obtain precise integral experimental data as the reactivity worth.

For these reasons, the sample temperature increasing device was developed, which is placed into the research reactor core to measure the sample temperature reactivity worth directly. The present paper introduces the device design, temperature increasing test results, and reactivity worth measurement results of the device.

2. OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH REACTOR AND PRESENT DEVICE

2.1. UTR-KINKI Research Reactor

The UTR-KINKI is a research reactor at Kindai University which has 1 W maximum thermal power. It consists of a light water-moderated fuel region and a graphite reflector, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. This core has a cuboid region at the center of the core, called the center stringer. Under the regulations, some samples can be inserted into this center stringer.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the core of UTR-KINKI.

Figure 4. Top view of the UTR-KINKI.

The regulations include a maximum reactivity insertion by the sample, maximum excess reactivity, and temperature. From the viewpoint of measurement of the sample temperature reactivity, the temperature

limitation is crucial. The Table I summarizes important regulations for the sample temperature increasing device.

The device surface temperature must be less than 60 °C based on the regulations; however, the design of this device aimed to keep it below 55 °C, which is the temperature considered for the safety margin. The sample case pressure regulation is defined as being below the pressure threshold subject to legal regulation of the fire act law. Furthermore, the safety rules of UTR-KINKI decided the maximum sample reactivity worth. The proposed sample temperature-increasing device was designed to satisfy these regulations.

Table I. Important Regulations for the sample temperature increasing device

Regulations	Value	Note
Device Surface Temperature	< 60 °C	Target:< 55 °C
Inner pressure	$\frac{\text{Gauge Pressure [MPa]}}{\text{Sample case volume [m}^3\text{]}} \geq 0.001$	
Sample reactivity worth	$\leq 0.3\%dk/k$	

2.2. Sample Temperature Increasing Device: Strauss

The Sample temperature-increasing device in the reactor core of UTR-KINKI for sample worth measurement, Strauss, consisted of a vacuum chamber and a sample unit, as shown in Figure 5. Moreover, Figure 6 shows the photo of the sample unit. The vacuum chamber stored the sample unit, which had four cartridge heaters for heating the sample holder.

The vacuum chamber is connected to the vacuum pump through the vacuum piping, and this vacuum pump decompresses the inside of this vacuum chamber around 1 Pa. Hence, the vacuum layer works as the insulator. As a result, although the temperature of the sample holder is up to 300 °C, and the surface temperature of the Strauss device can satisfy the regulation.

Figure 5. Schematic view of the Strauss device.

Figure 7 shows the result of the temperature-rising test of the Strauss device. Three thermocouples measured the temperature of the sample holder in CH2, and the top and bottom of the outer surface of the vacuum chamber in CH1 and CH4.

In this test, the sample holder was kept at 300 °C more than 25 minutes. However, the surface temperature of the vacuum chamber was below 46 °C. Thus, this test confirmed that the Strauss device satisfied the temperature regulation.

Figure 6. Inside of the *vacuum* chamber of the Strauss device.

Figure 7. Results of temperature rising test.

3. REACTIVITY WORTH

3.1. Worth of the Strauss Device

The reactivity worth of the Strauss device was measured to estimate the negative reactivity bias to the core. Figure 8 (a) and (b) show the assembled Strauss device and the Installed Strauss device into the center stringer of the UTR-KINKI.

In this experiment, two measurements were conducted to evaluate the reactivity worth of the Strauss, specifically, without the Strauss device, the Strauss was replaced by air (Empty case), and with the Strauss

device installed into the center stringer (Strauss case). On one hand, the Empty case achieved the criticality condition; on the other hand, the Strauss case did not achieve the criticality condition. Therefore, these measurements used positive and negative periods after the RR or neutron source extraction to evaluate the reactivity.

Figure 8. Assembled and installed Strauss device

Table II summarizes the measurement results of the Strauss device reactivity worth. The difference in measured reactivity between the Empty and the Strauss cases was -174.2 pcm. However, the Strauss case fully extracted the Regulation Rod (RR). Therefore, the worth of RR must be considered to evaluate the reactivity worth of the Strauss. Here, the reactivity worth of the RR is 126 pcm; as a result, the reactivity worth of the Strauss was 300.2 pcm. On the other hand, the simulated reactivity worth of the Strauss device, which was calculated based on the MVP-3.0 and JENDL4.0, was -265 pcm. The gap between experiment and simulated reactivity worth will be fixed by improving the simulation model in the next work.

Table II. Reactivity worth measurement of the Strauss device

	Rod position (%)	ρ (pcm)	dp from Empty case (pcm)	Reactivity worth considering RR rod (pcm)
Empty	SSR:100% RR:0%	81.43	-	
Strauss	SSR:100% RR:100%	-92.75	-174.2	-300.2

3.2. Worth of the CaH_2

The Monte Carlo simulation evaluated the worth of the CaH_2 sample. This calculation used MVP3.0 code and JENDL-4.0/JEFF-3.2 as the Monte Carlo neutron transportation code and the nuclear data libraries [8, 9, 10]. The JENDL-4.0 is generally used for neutronics calculations; however, the TSL data of CaH_2 is not stored in the JENDL. Therefore, JEFF-3.2 was used for the CaH_2 TSL data.

Figure 9 shows the geometry of the calculation model for the CaH_2 reactivity worth evaluation. The CaH_2 sample has a 30 mm diameter and a 100 mm height, and it was installed into the Strauss device. In this

model, the sample holder and vacuum chamber were made of aluminum; additionally, heaters were made of Nichrome. The temperature of the CaH_2 sample and the Strauss device were independently changed to evaluate each temperature reactivity worth.

Figure 9. *Geometry of the calculation model*

Figure 10 shows the calculated temperature reactivity characteristics of the Strauss device and the CaH_2 sample. The Strauss case did not show a clear trend due to the small impact on the thermal neutron spectrum; by contrast, the reactivity of the CaH_2 increased with the temperature, and it reached around 10 pcm, which is considered to originate from the thermal neutron equilibrium condition change. The spectrum shift to higher energy leads to a decrease of capture reaction in the structural material. Then, the positive reactivity of the CaH_2 temperature was expected. The UTR-KINKI can measure the reactivity with around 1 pcm precision; therefore, the temperature reactivity of the CaH_2 is expected to be measured by the Strauss device.

Figure 10. *Calculated temperature reactivity characteristics of the Strauss device and the CaH_2 sample*

4. CONCLUSION

The sample temperature increasing device in the reactor core of UTR-KINKI, Strauss, was developed to measure the sample temperature reactivity as the integral experiment data. This device can increase the sample temperature to 300 °C, and the available sample size is 30 mm in diameter and 100 mm in height. The regulation of surface temperature must be below 60 °C; however, it was kept less than 50 °C in the experiment.

The reactivity worth of the Strauss device is also measured based on the reactor period, and it was estimated to be around -300 pcm. Additionally, the temperature reactivity worth of the CaH₂ sample and the Strauss device was evaluated based on the calculation. As a result, the Strauss device did not show the trend; by contrast, the reactivity worth of the CaH₂ increased with the temperature up to 10 pcm at 300 °C. Therefore, the experiment using the **Strauss** device is expected to directly measure the temperature reactivity worth of the CaH₂ sample. Furthermore, since the Strauss device applies to various samples, this device will be available to experimentalists worldwide.

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